

Investigation of the Reactions of some New Fluorine containing 3-Aroylmethylene-indol-2-ones with Urea and Thiourea Derivatives

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In extension to our earlier interest on synthesis of biologically active indole derivatives¹, we report here the reaction of new fluorine containing 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**3**) with urea/thiourea leading to the synthesis of spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidin]-2(1*H*)-ones (**4**) along with 1,3-diazepino[4,5-*b*]indole-2-thiones/ones (**5**) for the first time; whereas, reaction of **3** with phenylurea/phenylthiourea afforded spiro[3*H*-indole-3, 4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidin]-2(1*H*)-one (**6**) ring system exclusively.

Literature survey reveals some contradictory reports on the reaction of 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**3**) with thiourea^{2,3}. Further, no attention has been paid earlier to the reaction of **3** with urea and phenylurea where the nature of nitrogen atom seems to be different which may alter the course of reaction. These facts prompted us to reinvestigate the title reaction.

3-Aroylmethyl-3-hydroxyindol-2-ones (**2**) prepared by the treatment of substituted isatin with fluorinated acetophenone, on dehydration with HCl-AcOH gave 3-arylmethylene-indol-2-ones (**3**). Compound **2** showed characteristic ir bands at 3 480 (OH), 3 300 (NH), 1 710 and 1 675 cm⁻¹ (both CO). ¹H nmr spectra revealed the characteristic peaks at δ 4.45 (1H, s, OH), 5.11 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.52-7.87 (7H, m, ArH). Ir spectra of compound **3** showed disappearance of OH band indicating conversion of **2** to extended conjugated system **3**, whose C=C absorption appeared at 1 620 cm⁻¹. In ¹H nmr spectra, instead of OH, a signal due to =CH proton was observed as a singlet at δ 4.28 in **3** along with the usual signals.

Compounds **4a-d** obtained by the reaction of **3** and

urea/thiourea, showed appearance of characteristic ir bands³ at 3 250-3 050 (NH), 1 710 (NHCO) and 1 600-1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Compounds **4a,c** showed additional band at 1 660 cm⁻¹ (pyrimidine C=O), whereas **4b,d** showed bands at 1 230 cm⁻¹ due to C=S^{3,4}. ¹H nmr spectra of **4a** showed signals at δ 4.66 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.10-7.24 (7H, m, ArH) and 9.49 (1H, s, NH). In mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 343 (*M*⁺) further confirmed the formation of **4a**. On the basis of spectral data, compound **4a** was identified as 5-chloro-6'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2',5'-dihydro-2'-oxospiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidin]-2(1*H*)-one.

Compounds **5a-d**, obtained by the reaction of **3** with urea/thiourea, exhibited complete disappearance of CO absorption (1 690-1 720 cm⁻¹) indicating involvement of both the keto groups on condensation. Other characteristic absorptions were observed at 3 100-3 230 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 230 cm⁻¹ (C=S). ¹H nmr spectra of compounds **5a-d** displayed peaks at δ 6.20 (1H, s, methine proton), 8.02 (1H, s, NH), 6.60-7.81 (7H, m, ArH). Further, the confirmation of both the keto groups being involved in the condensation reaction was obtained from the mass spectrum of the compound **5a** where the molecular ion peak was observed at *m/z* 325 (*M*⁺) by the loss of two water molecule in the reaction. On the basis of these observations, compound **5a** was identified as 7-chloro-4-(4-fluorophenyl)-1,3-diazepino[4,5-*b*]indol-2(1*H*)-one.

Similarly, compounds **6a-d** formed by the reaction of **3** with phenylurea/phenylthiourea, were characterised by the appearance of ir bands at 3 230-3 100 (NH), 1 715 (NHCO)^{5,6}, 1 660 (CO), 1 600 (C=N) and 1 240 cm⁻¹ (C=S). ¹H nmr spectrum of **6a** showed peaks at

δ 4.60 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.24–7.80 (12H, m, ArH) and 9.33 (1H, s, NH). Appearance of CO absorption ruled out the formation of a condensed system of the type 5. Mass spectrum of 6a showed molecular ion peak at m/z 419, confirming the formation of the spiro product.

The presence of fluorine in the compounds has been confirmed on the basis of ¹⁹F nmr spectra. Single fluorine attached to phenyl ring at 4-position was observed at –105.29 ppm as singlet.

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra on a Jeol Fx 90Q spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an external reference and using hexafluorobenzene (at –162.9 ppm) external reference for ¹⁹F nmr, and mass spectra on MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos mass spectrometers (70 eV).

Isatin derivatives (1) and 4-fluoroacetophenone were synthesised by literature method^{7,8}.

1,3-Dihydro-3-hydroxy-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethyl)-2H-indol-2-ones (2): A mixture of substituted indole-2,3-dione (1; .01 mol), 4-fluoroacetophenone (0.01 mol) and diethylamine (0.3 ml) in absolute ethanol (30–40 ml) was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. After standing for 48 h at room temperature, the pale yellow solid that separated was dried and crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd.	X	R	Yield %	M.p. (°C)
2a	Cl	F	66	186
2b	CH ₃	F	64	174
3a	Cl	F	68	154
3b	CH ₃	F	67	182

*Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

1,3-Dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2H-indol-2-ones (3): A mixture of 2, concentrated HCl (0.5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was heated for 15 min on a water-bath. On cooling, the bright red coloured crystalline compound thus obtained was dried in air and crystallised from ethanol.

Spiro[3H-indole-3,4'(3H)-pyrimidin]-2(1H)-one (4) and 1,3-diazepino[4,5-b]indole-2-thione/one (5): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and thiourea/urea (0.01 mol) in ethanolic KOH (30 ml) was refluxed for 4–6 h. On completion of the reaction, the mixture showed two spots on tlc. It was kept at room temperature overnight. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol and identified as condensed system 5. When the filtrate was allowed to stand further for 36 h, another

TABLE 2 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4–6*

Compd.	X	Y	R	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)
4a	Cl	O	4-F	24	198
b	Cl	S	4-F	20	264
c	CH ₃	O	4-F	25	308
d	CH ₃	S	4-F	22	342
5a	Cl	O	4-F	52	>360
b	Cl	S	4-F	55	>360
c	CH ₃	O	4-F	51	305
d	CH ₃	S	4-F	54	>360
6a	Cl	O	4-F	64	>360
b	Cl	S	4-F	66	>360
c	CH ₃	O	4-F	68	>360
d	CH ₃	S	4-F	64	>360

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

solid was obtained which was crystallised from ethanol and identified as spiro system **4**.

Spiro[3H-indole-3, 4'(3'H)-pyrimidin]-2(1H)-ones (6) : Under exactly similar conditions, reaction of **3** with phenylurea/phenylthiourea resulted in the formation of only one compound by keeping the solution for 24 h. The solid separated was crystallised from ethanol and identified as spiro product **6**. The filtrate when kept for several days did not give any product as obtained in the previous case.

All the other compounds were prepared in a similar manner. Analytical data of the compounds are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

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